

THE ORGANIZATIONAL MECHANISMS OF INTERNATIONAL TRADE

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Every nation strives to produce goods with a high added value while implementing international trade operations, and they all focus on this goal. It is only natural for every nation in the globe to have a plan for producing goods that can endure shifts in the global market and eventually find buyers.

By improving the standing of the goods produced by our nation's businesses on the international market, macroeconomic stability should be the ultimate objective of the socioeconomic changes being implemented in our nation [1].

The increased liberalization of international trade and the fortification of integration procedures into the global financial system are two significant trajectories of the globalization of the world economy for our nation. Notably, the clarifications that need to be made in this respect are to improve our nation's economic cooperation links with many other nations and to allow us to join the world's financial and economic organizations on an equal footing [2].

Achieving sustained economic development will depend in large part on taking further steps to support export-oriented businesses within the domestic economy, increase the export of competitive goods, draw in foreign direct investment, and fortify integration with the global economy [3].

Legal entities registered on the territory of the country, as well as individuals who have the citizenship of the country and operate as an individual entrepreneur, have the right to engage in international economic activity [4].

The Republic of Uzbekistan's Ministry of Investments, Industry, and Trade is the authority in charge of regulating our nation's foreign trade activities. Within the purview of international affairs, the Ministry has the following authorities: formulates a unified state policy for international trade activities and sees to it that it is carried out; oversees the work of state administration bodies in the area of international trade regulation; organizes and controls the activities of subjects of international trade activity within the parameters of their legislatively established authorities; and formulates recommendations for strengthening the legal foundation in this area.

The proper authorization (license) must be obtained before importing or exporting specific sorts of commodities into our nation. Trading across

international borders may only occur with a permission. The Republic of Uzbekistan's Cabinet of Ministers is a recognized authority that grants permits for the import or export of specific commodities.

Within its jurisdiction, the Cabinet of Ministers may impose quantitative limitations (quotas) on the trading of specific categories of products. Quotas are distributed by competition or auction.

The Republic of Uzbekistan's Cabinet of Ministers authorizes and restricts the conduct of foreign commercial activities. It also establishes the process for licensing and assigning quotas for the list of specific required goods categories.

A variety of forms and techniques for international commerce regulation have been created, in addition to state regulatory approaches. The actions of global organizations that oversee the majority of contemporary international commerce, as well as those of associations, groupings, and regional economic organizations, all reflect this. All nations objectively participate in the process of internationalizing economic life, which is increasingly a feature of the globalization process, even though their international trade policies are driven by their national economic interests (as well as the group interests of trade-economic blocs) [5].

As a result, the necessity of multilaterally coordinating international commerce is becoming increasingly pressing. This makes it possible to resolve issues like the "softening" of disputes between nations in a variety of areas related to international commerce, coming to a consensus, and maintaining consistency in how different nations and economic organizations regulate trade internationally.

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and the Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) are responsible for international trade regulation within the framework of the United Nations. Alongside them are the World Trade Organization (WORLD TRADE Organization, WTO) and the UNCTAD/WTO International Trade Center (ITS UNCTAD/WTO), both of which belong to the "Autonomous" category. In this, the WTO is the most significant player.

UNCTAD is a special permanent body of the UN that was founded in 1964. Three specialized agencies were represented at UNCTAD in 2000, together with 185 UN member states. UNCTAD's primary goals are to: advance international trade development to speed up economic growth and development, particularly in developing nations; establish policies and guidelines pertaining to trade and related issues of economic development, including finance, investment, and

technology transfer; assess and assist in coordinating the work of other UN agencies on trade and related issues of development; coordinating the trade and associated development strategies of states and regional economic organizations; conducting trade discussions and taking action to approve multilateral legal papers when appropriate.

UNCTAD's primary functions include: regulating trade and economic relations between nations, creating concepts and principles for the development of global trade, developing measures to control international trade in goods, creating trade policy tools and instruments, developing economic cooperation among developing nations, hosting conferences and expert and government representative meetings on diplomatic negotiations to coordinate national and regional economic groups' policies regarding the growth of global trade and other issues; regulation of restrictive business practices [6].

An important area of activity of UNCTAD is conducting analytical work on a wide range of issues. In 1996, the IX session of UNCTAD identified four main areas of this work: globalization and development; investment, enterprise and technology development; international trade of goods and services; development of infrastructure in the service sector.

UNCTAD publishes the following publications:

UNCTAD bulletin reports on least developed countries;
bulletin of transnational corporations, science and technology update, advanced technology assessment system;
sea transport review;
monthly commodity price bulletin.

In addition, UNCTAD provides a platform for discussions between various groups of nations on particular matters pertaining to international trade and development as well as for the debate and comparison of the stances taken by governments on general problems pertaining to international economic relations. UNCTAD also resolves issues related to collaboration with international economic organizations and assists in coordinating UN operations on matters pertaining to international trade [7].

It should be mentioned that our nation's integration into the global economy and its range of foreign economic activities contain well-defined objectives and steps taken to achieve them. A prerequisite is guaranteeing the exportability of domestic goods, providing avenues for ensuring their competitiveness and deserving position on the global market, and extensively utilizing state assistance techniques in the export-oriented economy.

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